

PRODUCTION OF THE JOSHI-EFFECT UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE

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Production of the Joshi-effect Δi , an instantaneous and reversible current decrease, on irradiation even in the visible is observed in a number of gases under (Siemens') ozonizer discharge at 0.1 to 4 kilo volts of 50 and 500 cycles. The effect increases with light-intensity and frequency; is sensitive to pressure changes of the excited gas. Hg vapour abolishes Δi in H_2 . Δi is not observed in neon and diminishes in the order: $Br > O_2 > air > N_2 > H_2$, which is approximately the order of their electron affinity, as suggested by Joshi.

Studies of the behaviour of nitrous oxide by Joshi (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 228; 1929, 25, 10, 118, 137, 143) and later in these laboratories of numerous physico-chemical reactions in various types of electrical discharge (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, p. 51; cf. also Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1939, 8, 548) showed the wide applicability of two deductions due to Joshi: (a) a discharge reaction sets in only above a 'threshold potential' V_m , where the medium breaks down as a dielectric; (b) the corresponding current i (as also the rate of the associated reaction) depends upon $V - V_m$, where V is the exciting potential. Following results for the H_2-Cl_2 union in electric discharge (Joshi and Bhargawa, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1937, p. 126; Joshi and Narsimhan, *ibid.*, 1939, Part III, p. 57) Joshi observed a photo-increase of V_m in chlorine. From this and (b), Joshi predicted a current decrease Δi in light, a consequence at variance with the current theories of photo-electric and discharge reactions. This predicted Δi reported by Joshi in 1938 (*vide* Joshi, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, A 22, 389; *Curr. Sci.*, 1944, 13, 253; Tiwari and Prasad, *ibid.*, 1945, 14, 229; Das-Gupta, *Science & Culture*, 1945, 11, 318) is confirmed by numerous results in these laboratories and elsewhere (especially in Cl_2 in which the Joshi-effect Δi is most pronounced) over a wide range of conditions. Extension of Δi to other systems (Joshi and Deshmukh, *Nature*, 1941, 147, 806) restricted by available means, were halted repeatedly by difficulties as the corresponding Δi is much smaller than in Cl_2 and also very sensitive to changes in operative conditions (Joshi and Deo, *Nature*, 1943, 151, 561). This paper reports results for the Joshi-effect Δi in bromine vapour, air, N_2 , O_2 , H_2 and Ne in Siemens' tubes.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general experimental arrangement and the circuit are shown in Fig. 1. The discharge vessel consisted of two glass tubes sealed together co-axially as in a Siemens' ozonizer. This was enclosed in a wooden box with a sliding shutter S; it enabled irradiating the ozoniser without disturbing the rest of the arrangement.

The manometer M recorded the pressure of the gas in the discharge tube. By proper manipulation of the taps T_1 — T_6 , the whole or any desired part of the apparatus could be connected to the Töpler and the Warran pumps W_1 and W_2 .

FIG. 1.

The liquid air traps L_1 and L_2 were used for condensing the mercury vapour (which is found to affect the Joshi-effect, vide *infra*) emanating from the Warran pumps and also for freeing the gas under investigation from traces of any other condensable impurities. Each of the gases was dried carefully by leading it slowly through a series of tubes containing phosphorus pentoxide, calcium chloride and potassium hydroxide and stored finally in the reservoir R . The main experiment was commenced only when the entire assembly maintained a satisfactory vacuum for at least 48 hours.

Single phase alternating currents of 50 and 500 cycle frequencies were obtained from rotary converters worked off 220 volt D. C. mains. The output was fed to the primary of a step-up transformer (Fig. 1). One of its secondary terminals was earthed; the other was connected to the high tension i.e. the inner electrode of the ozonizer. The potential in the primary V was recorded with an A. C. voltmeter. The secondary potential kV (kilo volts r.m.s.) was calculated from a knowledge of V and the step-up ratio of the transformer. A reflection type galvanometer, actuated by a Cambridge vacuo-junction, introduced in the low tension part of the ozonizer circuit, served to indicate the current i . The galvanometer deflections were observed on a scale at 5 meters from the galvanometer; these

readings are accurate to the second decimal place. The current i was measured (i) in dark and (i_1) under irradiation from an external light source, by manipulation of the shutter S, the bulb (or its substitute, *vide infra*) being switched on previously at the desired voltage.

The choice of irradiation depended principally on the nature of the gas under investigation. Thus, for example, in the case of bromine vapour, which showed a comparatively large Joshi-effect Δi , when excited at different applied potentials of 50 cycles frequency, a 220 volt, 200 watt incandescent (glass) bulb was used. With this light-source Δi was scarcely detectable in oxygen, air, nitrogen and hydrogen, excited at 500 cycles frequency. A quartz-mercury vapour lamp of large size was therefore used in their case. This was further supplemented by two large size carbon arcs in the case of neon; for this last, two neon discharge tubes of large size were also used as light source (*cf.* Table VI).

Bromine vapour was obtained from a bulb containing pure liquid bromine. This was first cooled by liquid air when bromine froze to a solid with a negligible vapour pressure. This bulb was then connected to a trap (which was cooled by liquid air) and then to the ozonizer in Fig. 1. This was then evacuated through the taps T₁—T₃ with the Töpler to remove any uncondensable impurities. The liquid air was then removed carefully and bromine allowed to vaporise. The ozonizer was filled with the middle fraction of the vaporised bromine. The bromine bulb was then sealed off. The results for Δi in bromine vapour at about 200 mm. pressure, excited in the range 1-4 kV (50 cycles), are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Joshi-effect in bromine vapour.

Frequency of the A.C. supply = 50 cycles sec.⁻¹

Source of irradiation = 220 volt, 200 watt bulb.

kV.	(Unpolarised)		Δi .	% Δi .	(Polarised)		Δi .	% Δi .
	Galvo deflection				Galvo deflection			
	Dark.	Light.			Dark.	Light.		
1.8	4.5 (2.12)	4.1 (2.0)	0.12	5.7	4.4 (2.09)	4.2 (2.04)	0.05	2.4
1.8	6.2 (2.49)	5.6 (2.36)	0.18	5.2	6.0 (2.45)	5.6 (2.36)	0.09	3.7
2.7	10.1 (3.18)	8.8 (2.96)	0.22	6.9	9.8 (3.13)	8.9 (2.98)	0.15	4.8
3.5	14.8 (3.84)	12.7 (3.56)	0.26	7.3	14.0 (3.74)	12.9 (3.5)	0.24	6.8

Oxygen was obtained by heating pure potassium chlorate in a small, hard glass bulb sealed to the apparatus. The bulb containing the chlorate was evacuated thoroughly and then heated slowly just above the fusion temperature of the chlorate. The first portion of the evolved gas was rejected by the Töpler; the middle portion was passed over heated magnesium powder to remove any traces of nitrogen. The gas was dried carefully over phosphorus pentoxide and then admitted to the

ozonizer at the desired pressure by the manipulation of the taps T_4 and T_5 in Fig. 1. Since compared with bromine, Δi was very much smaller in other gases, the frequency of the A.C. supply used was increased to 500 cycles with all of them; this greatly increased the current i at the same applied V . The observation of the corresponding current change was expected therefore to be more accurate. Table II refers to the results obtained for Δi in oxygen at 22 and 36 mm. pressures at 0.1 to 0.4 kV applied to the ozonizer.

TABLE II

*Joshi-effect in oxygen.*Frequency of the A.C. supply = 500 cycles sec.⁻¹

Source of irradiation = Mercury vapour lamp.

Pressure of O ₂ = 2.2 cm. Hg.					Pressure of O ₂ = 3.6 cm. Hg.				
kV.	Galvo deflection		Δi .	% Δi .	kV.	Galvo deflection		Δi .	% Δi .
	Dark.	Light.				Dark.	Light.		
0.18	48.0 (8.92)	44.0 (8.63)	0.29	4.2	0.18	44.0 (8.63)	42.2 (8.57)	0.06	0.9
0.21	102.0 (10.1)	94.5 (9.72)	0.36	3.7	0.21	97.0 (9.84)	93.5 (9.66)	0.18	1.9
0.27	123.0 (11.09)	114.0 (10.69)	0.41	3.7	0.27	115.0 (10.72)	109.0 (10.44)	0.28	2.4
0.32	151.0 (12.29)	141.5 (11.9)	0.39	3.1	0.32	142.0 (11.92)	132.0 (11.51)	0.42	3.5

Air was freed carefully from carbon dioxide and moisture by leading it slowly through a train of tubes containing potassium hydroxide, phosphorus pentoxide and calcium chloride. The data for the Joshi-effect at 0.2 to 0.4 kV of 500 cycles frequency in air are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

*Joshi-effect in air.*Frequency of the A.C. supply = 500 cycles sec.⁻¹.

Source of irradiation = Mercury vapour lamp.

Pressure of air = 2.8 cm. Hg.					Pressure of air = 3.6 cm. Hg.				
kV.	Galvo deflection		Δi .	% Δi .	kV.	Galvo deflection		Δi .	% Δi .
	Dark.	Light.				Dark.	Light.		
0.27	46.0 (6.78)	43.2 (6.57)	0.21	3.1	0.27	41.0 (6.04)	40.8 (6.02)	0.02	0.3
0.35	86.0 (9.27)	81.5 (9.02)	0.25	2.7	0.32	74.0 (8.8)	72.5 (8.51)	0.09	1.0
0.37	119.0 (10.91)	113.5 (10.65)	0.26	2.4	0.37	99.0 (9.9)	93.5 (9.66)	0.12	1.2
0.40	131.0 (11.46)	124.0 (11.14)	0.31	2.7					

Nitrogen was obtained from a commercial cylinder. The gas was bubbled carefully through a series of absorption bulbs containing a freshly prepared solution of alkaline pyrogallol and then led very slowly over strongly heated copper turnings to remove traces of oxygen. This gas was dried carefully over phosphorus pentoxide and then introduced in the ozonizer. Results for Δi at 0.2 to 0.5 kV of 500 cycles frequency in nitrogen are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Joshi-effect in nitrogen.

 Frequency of the A.C. supply = 500 cycles sec.⁻¹.

Source of irradiation - Mercury vapour lamp.

Pressure of N ₂ = 2.6 cm. Hg.					Pressure of N ₂ = 4.1 cm. Hg.				
kV.	Galvo deflection		Δi .	% Δi .	kV.	Galvo deflection		Δi .	% Δi .
	Dark.	Light.				Dark.	Light.		
0.21	35.0 (5.91)	34.0 (5.83)	0.08	1.3	0.24	18.0	18.0	—	—
0.27	58.0 (7.61)	55.5 (7.46)	0.16	2.1	0.32	31.0 (5.56)	30.2 (5.49)	0.07	1.26
0.32	76.0 (8.71)	72.5 (8.51)	0.20	2.2	0.37	41.5 (6.44)	39.0 (6.24)	0.20	3.1
0.37	94.0 (9.7)	90.0 (9.48)	0.22	2.2	0.43	51.0 (7.4)	48.0 (6.92)	0.22	3.1

Hydrogen was prepared by the electrolysis of a dilute aqueous solution of pure baryta. The gas was bubbled slowly through a freshly prepared solution of alkaline pyrogallol and then over heated copper turnings and magnesium powder, in order to remove any traces of oxygen and nitrogen respectively. It was then dried by passing over phosphorus pentoxide and calcium chloride and finally admitted to the ozonizer at the desired pressure. Data for the Joshi-effect in hydrogen at 500 cycles frequency in the range 0.1 to 0.4 kV are recorded in Table V. In observing the influence of mercury vapour on the corresponding Joshi-effect in hydrogen, the apparatus was evacuated as described earlier without cooling the traps L₁ and L₂ by liquid air, which served to condense mercury; instead, hydrogen was led over heated mercury in the Warran pumps W₁ and W₂ before entering the ozonizer. As shown in the lower half of Table V, Δi was not detectable on saturating hydrogen at 34 mm. pressure with mercury vapour.

TABLE V

Joshi-effect in hydrogen.

 Frequency of the A. C. supply = 500 cycles sec.⁻¹

Source of irradiation - Hg vapour lamp.

Pressure of H ₂ = 1.7 cm. Hg.					Pressure of H ₂ = 6.7 cm. Hg.				
kV.	Galvo deflection		Δi .	% Δi .	kV.	Galvo deflection		Δi .	% Δi .
	Dark.	Light.				Dark.	Light.		
0.13	88.0 (9.36)	87.0 (9.32)	0.06	0.06	0.21	18.0	19.0	—	—
0.16	131.0 (11.46)	128.0 (11.30)	0.15	1.3	0.27	79.0	79.0	—	—
0.19	150.0 (12.24)	144.0 (12.0)	0.25	2.4	0.30	140.6	140.6	—	—
0.20	185.0 (13.6)	176.0 (13.27)	0.33	2.4	0.32	166.0	166.0	—	—

TABLE V (contd.)

Pressure of H ₂ = 3.3 cm. Hg.					Pressure of H ₂ (mixed with Hg vapour) = 3.4 cm. Hg.				
kV.	Galvo deflection		Δi .	% Δi .	kV.	Galvo deflection		Δi .	% Δi .
	Dark.	Light.				Dark.	Light.		
0.13	46.0 (6.76)	45.4 (6.73)	0.05	0.7	0.13	43.0	43.0	—	—
0.16	126.0 (11.22)	123.0 (11.09)	0.13	1.1	0.16	105.0	105.0	—	—
0.19	168.0 (12.96)	165.0 (12.84)	0.12	0.8	0.19	174.0	174.0	—	—
0.27	204.5 (14.3)	198.5 (14.1)	0.20	1.3					

In experiments with neon the ozonizer was first evacuated as completely as possible using Töpler and Warran pumps. A high frequency discharge was passed through the ozonizer and the process of evacuation continued to ensure complete removal of any traces of impurities adsorbed on the walls of the ozonizer. Neon was then introduced at a small pressure and subjected to electrical discharge and the system was again evacuated. This process was repeated till a spectroscopically pure sample of the gas was obtained in the ozonizer. The gas pressure employed was 23 mm. These results for neon, excited in the range of 0.1 to 1.0 kV (500 cycles) and irradiated by a quartz-mercury vapour lamp, two carbon arcs and neon discharge tubes (all of large size), are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI

*Joshi-effect in neon.*Frequency of the A. C. supply = 500 cycles sec.⁻¹

Pressure of neon = 2.3 cm. Hg.

 Δi & % Δi — nil.

Source of irradiation = Hg vapour lamp.			Source of irradiation = 2 carbon arcs.			Source of irradiation = 2 Neon discharge tubes.		
kV.	Galvo deflection		kV.	Galvo deflection		kV.	Galvo deflection	
	Dark.	Light.		Dark.	Light.		Dark.	Light.
0.13	3.0	3.0	0.43	14.0	14.0	0.32	8.0	8.0
0.16	11.2	11.2	0.50	25.0	25.0	0.59	47.6	47.6
0.21	16.6	16.6	0.59	47.0	47.0	0.63	102.0	102.0
			0.67	56.0	56.0	0.68	172.0	172.0
			0.83	102.0	102.0			
			1.0	178.0	178.0			

Fig. 2 shows characteristic current deflection-potential curves for the above gases in dark and in light with appropriate scale units (*cf.* Tables I-VI). The discharge current i is given by the square root of the corresponding deflection in Fig. 2 (and shown within brackets under the corresponding deflections in Tables I-VI), the decrease of i in dark under light gives the net Joshi-effect Δi under given

conditions ; the relative Joshi-effect is shown by $\% \Delta i$. It is seen, *e.g.*, in the case of bromine vapour (Table I) that the decrease (under light) in the current deflection is 9 to 14% as the applied potential is increased from 1.3 to 3.5 kV. The much less reduced values for $\% \Delta i$ are due to the circumstance that i depends upon the

FIG. 2.

square root of the corresponding galvanometer deflection ; this renders both Δi and $\% \Delta i$ more accurate than the deflection changes on irradiation. The quantities Δi and $\% \Delta i$, as reported in Tables I-VI, are such that changes in deflection less than five times the accuracy of observation are not considered.

DISCUSSION

The foregoing results serve to establish that (under the range of operative conditions employed in this work) with the exception of neon, the Joshi-effect Δi occurs in the various gases investigated, *viz.*, bromine, oxygen, air, nitrogen and hydrogen. An appreciable Δi is to be anticipated in bromine vapour by analogy of its nature with chlorine. That Δi characteristic of bromine is much greater than that in any of the other gases, now studied, is shown by the fact that, it is 5.7% (*cf.* Table I) with light from a 200 watt bulb and a current of 50 cycles frequency ; whereas Δi is not detected in any of the other gases using mercury arc irradiation, which has a far greater intensity, both over-all and in the short wave-

(therefore, photoactive) region. Also even with this light, in contrast with bromine, Δi was observable in any of the above gases only when the total conductivity was enhanced by using a much larger current frequency, viz., 500 cycles; with this last and the bulb light Δi was not observed in the above gases.

The characteristic current-potential curves for dark and light in Fig. 2, show that the net Joshi-effect Δi in any gas increases by increasing the applied potential kV. The corresponding relative effect $\% \Delta i$, however, diminishes over the potential range investigated, viz., 0.1 to 4 kilo volts (r.m.s.) except in the case of bromine vapour. Subsequent work has shown that $\% \Delta i$ even in bromine diminishes with a large enough applied potential; this has been specified to be a general characteristic of this phenomenon by Joshi (*loc. cit.*).

Joshi (*loc. cit.*) and Joshi and Deo (*loc. cit.*) have emphasized that Δi is determined by several factors, e.g., nature of the electrode surface, its area, spacing and 'ageing' under the discharge, various electrical quantities, nature, temperature and especially the pressure of the excited gas (Joshi and Deo, *Nature*, 1944, 153, 434).

The chief difficulty in ascertaining the optimum conditions for Δi and its comparative values in different gases, is that more than a restricted change of one of these factors alters the magnitude of others and therefore reduces the comparability of results. The following deduction can, however, be made from results in Fig. 2: With mercury arc light a gas pressure varied over 25 to 35 mm. Hg. excited over 0 to 0.3 kV of 500 cycles, the Joshi-effect Δi varies in the order: oxygen > air > nitrogen > hydrogen. That Δi in bromine vapour exceeds markedly that in any of the other gases studied has been shown already. The above order for Δi in the various gases would appear to be also their order in respect of the 'electron affinity', which has been emphasized by Joshi to be an important determinant of Δi . Their relative adsorbability (both ionic and molecular, on the excited walls of the ozonizer) is possibly another factor. This is also suggested by the marked influence on Δi of saturating hydrogen with mercury vapour (Table V). Work is in progress to investigate this result in more detail. It is also seen that Δi is more pronounced at a low initial pressure p . The apparent reduction in Δi with bromine vapour (Table I) with light transmitted through a polaroid has been attributed to the reduction of the corresponding intensity as distinct from an effect due to light polarisation. The production of Δi in gases other than halogens suggests that it may be different from the well known Budde effect.

Results recorded in Table VI (of only one typical series) show that within the limitations of these experimental conditions the Joshi-effect Δi is absent in excited neon despite the various intense irradiations employed. The possibility of Δi being due to destruction of the metastable atoms was examined in the case of hydrogen (*cf.* Table V). Penning (*Phil. Mag.*, 1931, 11 961) has found that about 0.0001% of mercury vapour reduced the 'starting potential' of neon by about 20%. The energy of the metastable neon atom viz., 16.6 volts is sufficient for the ionisation

of mercury, which occurs at 10.4 volts. When, however, the mixture is exposed to an external neon light, the metastable neon atoms are considered by Penning to be destroyed and the corresponding starting potential is raised as a consequence. Since the ionisation potential of mercury is less than that of hydrogen viz., 13.3 volts, an increase of the 'starting potential' and therefore on Joshi's view that i depends on $(V - V_m)$, a current decrease like Δi should occur in the hydrogen mercury vapour mixture on irradiation. The negative results using a quartz-mercury vapour lamp (Table V) seem therefore to discriminate the Joshi-effect from the phenomenon observed by Penning. Similar observations are not possible with bromine vapour, oxygen and air in view of a possible chemical reaction between mercury and these gases.

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